

Evaluation of human resource management of expressway operation enterprise: Basis for enhanced human resource

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Abstract

This study mainly analyzes the current situation and problems of human resource management at S company under the rapid development of intelligence and puts forward countermeasures to improve human resource management at S high-speed operation enterprise so as to provide reference for human resource management at other companies in the same industry. A total of 89 questionnaires were sent out in this survey, and 81 valid questionnaires were finally collected, with an effective recovery rate of 91%. Problems in human resource management were identified in a high-speed operation company. The study mentioned that the staff demands of the parent company of the S high-speed operation company gradually tend to be saturated, which will cause certain obstacles to the re-employment of high-speed toll collection employees. It can be found that the overall evaluation of the company's employees is low in the whole process of recruitment. The four indicators are investigated, respectively, and it is found that the assessment from high to low refers to the standardization of recruitment procedures, recruitment channels, job analysis, and the competency of the recruitment staff. The results also showed that respondents did not agree with the evaluation of the company's training management; however, the degree of evaluation varies from top to bottom, and the interest in the training methods of S Company is more obvious in the field of training management. The research suggested that the company should improve relevant systems, properly solve the re-employment problem of employees, pay attention to reasonable methods in the implementation process, and actively and promptly deal with it.

Keywords: *Human resource management; expressway operation enterprise; enhanced human resource.*

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Introduction

As a highway worker, I am proud of the achievements of highway construction and development in G province in the past 30 years. Since 1993, G province has built the first highway and, up to now, has built nearly 7,000 kilometers of highway network. This can be said to be very rapid development because the promotion of urban construction and the urbanization process have played an important role. With the rapid development of intelligent highways, I am worried about the long-term development of traditional expressway operation enterprises, especially expressway human resource management, against the background of intelligent high-speed development.

Intelligent highways integrate perception, control, and service. At present, traditional expressways have shortcomings such as fragmentary information collection, passive post-processing, and discontinuous push service. Based on the exploration and experimentation in various places, smart highway has not yet formed a standard definition and functional framework, but the development concept of digitization of facilities, transportation automation, proactive management, and personalized service has been basically established and accelerated to maturity and presents the following development characteristics:

With the help of high-definition videos, Beidou positioning, dedicated sensors, and other types of monitoring equipment, the construction of a total factor, a full-time and space perception system, a high-quality collection of highway data, and high-reliability transmission is the key to promoting the application of accompanying information services, real-time traffic management, and other applications. The mining based on total factor and whole time and space perception data will better promote high-speed intelligent upgrade iteration. Refined management and control to improve high-speed efficiency. Based on highway intelligence, dynamic and static operation data analysis can accurately identify critical ramp or anticipation, bottlenecks, and main flow channels, and assign a dynamic on-ramp control, shoulder control, drive control, and active control rate adjustment strategy to realize the traffic ahead to guide and control, greatly improving the capacity of highway traffic and emergency disposal. New technology opens up new business spaces. The current highway business model has a very low ceiling. However, in the future, new business models such as formation driving, wireless charging, and subscription services will see explosive growth based on new technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, fusion perception, autonomous driving, and vehicle-road collaboration, which will greatly expand the business space of smart highways.

The next 10 years will be a golden decade of rapid development of wisdom and mind. In the context of a strong transportation country, it has become a consensus to build a smart highway. For example, on the eve of the launch of smart cars equipped with autonomous driving technology, smart highways should make preparations for smart cars in advance, which is also in line with the principle of moderately advanced infrastructure construction advocated by the state. Only the construction of moderately advanced infrastructure can take advantage of the new round of reform so that new technologies, new models, and new products can better develop towards industrialization, marketization, and scale. According to the current economic development trend, the national demand for cargo transportation will continue to grow at a rate of 2%–3% per year, while the growth rate in the Yangtze River Delta, Pearl River Delta, and Beijing and Tianjin will be twice as fast as the national rate.

In about 15 years, the road network will have to carry twice as much traffic as it does now. This is a very realistic problem that we have to face. We not only need to plan, build, and operate the existing expressways well, but we also need to bring users a real sense of gain with long-term layout, innovative technical concepts, and service modes. As an important digital infrastructure in the field of intelligent transportation, intelligent high-speed has become the commanding height of deployment in the world. As China's economic development enters a new cycle, focusing on the development of modern infrastructure systems centered on smart highways has become one of the most important means to change the mode of economic development. The construction of intelligent expressways will facilitate the innovation and development of application scenarios, including intelligent monitoring, intelligent scheduling, intelligent control, and intelligent services. The construction of intelligent highways will also accelerate the commercialization process of autonomous driving and promote the landing of self-driving application scenarios. Looking into the future, new business models such as formation driving, wireless charging, and subscription services will see explosive growth based on new technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, fusion perception, autonomous driving, and vehicle-road collaboration, which will greatly expand the business space of smart highways.

Human resources are an important resource that plays a very important role in the development of all walks of life. For expressway enterprises, if they want to achieve long-term development under the general trend of intelligent rapid development, they need to pay attention to human resource management and build a perfect human resource management mechanism so as to give full play to the human effect and achieve further improvement of enterprise benefits.

Theoretical Framework

Two-factor Theory

In the United States in the late 1950s, Herzberg and his co-authors interviewed more than 200 engineers and businessmen in the Pittsburgh area about their work status and what their companies needed to do to motivate them (Herzberg et al., 1959). In the interview process of the survey, two questions are mainly focused on. The first question is whether there are any things or tasks that they like to hear during working hours that will make workers happy. On the contrary, the second question is what specific things they are not satisfied with and do not want to hear. By comparing the results of the survey, it is easy to find that what makes the employees satisfied is mainly the problems within the company, and the specific performance is the internal factor of the work itself or the task, while what makes them dissatisfied is no longer the internal relationship of the company, but the specific performance is mainly the external factor of the working situation or the employment relationship.

Hertzberg et al. defines the first motivation and the second motivation as motivators and health factors. In this process, the wellness factor can also be called the maintenance factor because it has no incentive payment but has the benefit of maintaining the current situation and preventing it. Just as health care can prevent the occurrence of diseases, the preventive effect is completely different from the curative effect; it cannot directly improve health. Although there is no treatment, a lack of health care will also have a corresponding result: one is a non-negative effect, and the other is a negative effect. Health factors include policies, regulatory frameworks, reporting, job requirements, income, and benefits that are relevant to the company you work for. When these factors are not humane enough to reach an acceptable level for employees, the problem arises that employees may become dissatisfied with their jobs, which increases their negative attitude towards work. However, if we consider these factors to be good, we can only eliminate the dissatisfaction and not bring out the positive state of work; that is, it does not lead to a positive attitude towards work, which creates a neutral state of neither satisfaction nor dissatisfaction.

The difference between the motivation factor and the health factor is that they mainly affect the internal factor of people's attitude at work. For example, the challenge of the work content and the subsequent responsibility to the end can satisfy personal career growth and understanding of the plan, and recognition and the acquisition of a sense of achievement can be very satisfying. In addition to satisfaction, there are a lot of incentives. These factors do not exist and will not cause employee dissatisfaction, but their existence ensures employee satisfaction and a positive working attitude, depending on the number of satisfied employees and positive problems. Just as physical exercise can improve physical fitness and promote health, but physical exercise does not necessarily lead to absolutely no illness, lack of motivation has only two consequences: positive and negative effects. In a word, employees should first be recognized for external factors, that is, those related to the working environment and working relationship. Otherwise, employees may not be in a positive state at work. Traditional incentives, such as good wages, good relationships, and working conditions that meet the requirements of employees, do not create incentives. They can only eliminate people's dissatisfaction and avoid problems, but even if they are optimal, the positive effects will not appear. The internal factors of the job itself and the job content are reversed. Without these factors, there will be no negative impact. However, the great satisfaction of employees can be brought about by these factors, and then more enthusiasm and innovation among employees can be stimulated.

Human Resource Management Theory

Human resources is an important concept in enterprise management. Generally speaking, human resource management refers to the management behavior of an organization in the aspects of planning, acquisition, maintenance, incentive, and evaluation. From its internal human resources to achieve its management objectives. It is the gradual development of personnel management into human resource management, which is the follow-up, development, expansion, deepening, and transcendence of human resource management. In the content of human resource management, people are regarded as a kind of resource, in addition to the development and planning of human resources, all of which contain certain adaptability, changeableness, and invariability. Staff planning should require consideration of the objectives of the organization, in-depth analysis of the environment, and projections of staffing levels.

Of all the management functions, the most strategic and forward-looking is human resource planning. With this, society and technology will certainly continue to develop along with the pace of progress. At the same time, the environment is also constantly changing, which brings about the result that the difficulty of human resources planning, and prediction is constantly increasing. Human resource management is the focus of expressway electronic toll collection (ETC) operation management. Human resources are the first resource; good human resource management has an incentive effect on the construction and development of highway enterprises. With the popularity of ETC in the operation and management of expressways, it should be noted that the “people-oriented” principle should be followed by human resource management. Reasonable allocation, use, and training of human resources will play a good role in improving the technical content, use, and operation efficiency of ETC, contributing to better development, making better contributions to everyone, and obtaining greater social returns.

In this paper, human resources are defined as the sum of labor capacity existing at a certain time and space. Human resources are characterized by subjective initiative, inseparability with the human body, and timeliness. Human resources are the sum of the mechanisms, systems, processes, technologies, and methods that effectively develop, rationally utilize, and scientifically manage the members of the organization according to the development goals of the organization, so as to give full play to the potential of the organization and further achieve the goals of the organization.

Literature Review

By referring to all the research on human resource management of highway operation enterprises abroad, the highway will be public. Road enterprises are studied as general enterprises. Among them, there is the most research on the organizational structure of highway companies.

The core of technological change will also be the workers because the labor force is the core of the enterprise, and their work has become an important part of the enterprise policy. Like in *The Wealth of Nations*, Adam Smith also put forward the idea of human resources (Spalletti, 2014). Carmona-Moreno et al. (2012) believe that the work of employees is very important to the role of the company. From the perspective of checking the basic skills, in order to improve the competitiveness of the enterprise further on the basis of the original, attention should be paid to the unification of the ability transfer between different functions of the enterprise, that is, the coordination between different functions.

With the development and daily reform of the enterprise, employee motivation, which plays an important role in the internal tasks of the enterprise, is still the comprehensive force of the enterprise to seek the interests of the enterprise. In today's increasingly fierce market competition, an important part of the company is a large proportion of employees, supporting the increasing improvement of market competitiveness. It is also important content to further improve the company's management, support the total amount, and enhance the company's strength.

As one of the members of the company management team, I should establish the organizational structure according to the overall work flow of the organization and make the overall plan for human resource management. From the perspective of analysis, I can optimize the overall strength of the enterprise. By helping to optimize human resource management, the joint strength of the company can be further enhanced. The support is mainly for the company to carry out the correct operation and management work, but also to ensure the further optimization of management levels and the improvement of business market competitiveness.

Abdullah et al. (2009) put forward the construction of a human resources management department, which is mainly set up for the modernization of the company, the overall arrangement and systematic management of the company's human resources management, and at the same time to meet the current situation. Li (2021) analyzed the human resources management of expressway operating enterprises under the comprehensive popularization of ETC. The present situation and development path of management are explored and studied. Liu (2016) discussed and analyzed the current situation and countermeasures of talent development in the non-public economy in Shaanxi Province. Wei (2020) studied the problems and measures faced by human resource management in transportation enterprises under the new economic normal. Guifang (2014) studied problems and countermeasures in the human resources management of transportation enterprises. On the basis of the research on the human resource management of high-speed operating enterprises, many scholars focused on the discussion and analysis of the HRM mode of high-speed operating enterprises. For example, Yan (2020) studied and analyzed the HRM mode analysis of the current situation and countermeasures in transportation management units.

Li (2021) believes that human resource management is the foundation of a company's work and the first task of an enterprise. It is to maintain the enterprise organization and promote the further promotion and management of the company. At the same time, accompanied by technological transformation, it is required to improve the optimization of human resource management, which requires that the vacancy in human resource management can meet the actual needs of the enterprise to support the good operation and management of the enterprise. From the moment the business environment changes, an important part of the comprehensive strength of the enterprise is highlighted: human resource management.

Bloom and van Reenen (2011) said that the most effective and direct management means and ways for enterprises are to do a good job in human resources management. The structure of human resources will also change with the transformation of enterprise functions; that is, human resource management is an important task. In the process of better management and further efforts, human resource management optimization must be fully reflected in human-centeredness in order to succeed in the previous established programs, so that the comparison of human resource management can also be effectively managed. Therefore, the management of employees is valued, which is also an important content of enterprise management. Combined with the needs of modern enterprise management systems, the goal of human resource management must fully reflect the comprehensive strength of the enterprise. The most effective management strategy in enterprise management has become human resource management.

Liu (2017) indicates that it has formed a certain scale and influence in the market, mainly the scale and competitiveness of highway enterprises, formed in the actual situation of the market, and the automated development of human resource structure changes will occur, which requires enterprises to work out relevant strategies in human resource management under the guidance of the strategy. Human resource management further improves management objectives and implements effective measures under the guidance of collectivization. Therefore, the achievements in this aspect are not enough to climb to a higher level. Under the guidance of an enterprise development strategy, we should explore the development of enterprises and pay attention to various aspects, not only to support the development of enterprises but also to professionalize employees. It is to carry out targeted training for employees on a daily basis to support the development, service level, and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Lin (2016) mainly proposed that human resource management must adapt to the changing needs of the work content of the enterprise so as to create different workplaces, distinguish between units and administrative units for promotion and sales-related policies, and explain their own needs in different positions. In the process of management, enterprises should propose and explain that they can meet the needs of employees in various functions and stimulate and support their enthusiasm for work, which is also an important content and effective measure of quality management for enterprises with rapid development. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate long-term plans for the development of staff in different positions so as to improve the comprehensive competitiveness of enterprises, reduce the loss of staff, and increase the stability of staff.

From the research literature at home and abroad, it can be inferred that the field of human resources in the expressway society has developed relatively maturely, can make effective solutions to the existing problems, and has a relatively perfect management system. As the Ministry of Transport wants to vigorously expand ETC, it has changed the demand for the talents of highway enterprises, and the original management system can no longer solve the current business problems. In this paper, under the challenge of human resources for highway operating companies in G province, aiming at the general problems of the management of highway operating companies and the effect of the distribution of problems, this paper summarizes the existing problems in human resources management and puts forward the corresponding solutions so as to further optimize and improve the quality of human resources management. Although there is much systematic research literature on human resource management at home and abroad, there is not much research on the transportation industry. Through long-term collection and collation, the available materials are very limited, and the literature on case studies of a specific company is almost blank. By referring to domestic and foreign research results and using the case analysis method, the current situation of human resource management at S Company is decomposed and explained in detail. Problems are identified, and solutions to optimize human resource management are proposed so as to comprehensively cope with future problems and achieve sustainable development for the company.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

First of all, understand the relevant requirements of the paper and master the research methods and relevant theories applied in this paper so as to determine the direction and main line of the paper writing, so as to provide a good foundation for the paper writing simply and quickly. Secondly, in the paper, on the basis of the outline, the first thing to do is to provide national major policy direction and wisdom on the construction of high-speed collection wisdom under the background of comprehensive promotion, drive the related questions of human resource management, combined with the real demand of enterprises, and for S Highway Management Company, put forward the corresponding solutions with detailed technical routes and guidelines.

The limitations of this study are mainly in two aspects: 1. China has a vast territory, and there is a big gap in economic development level between different regions, so there is a big gap in smart highway construction. This paper only studies human resource management under the high level of smart highway construction, which has certain limitations. 2. With the rapid development of wisdom, the development direction in the next few years may be different from the present stage, resulting in improper content for this study.

Statement of the Problem

This study mainly analyzes the current situation and problems of human resource management at S company under the rapid development of intelligence and puts forward countermeasures to improve human resource management at S high-speed operation enterprise so as to provide reference for human resource management at other companies in the same industry.

1. What is the profile of enterprise in terms of:
 - a. Ownership
 - b. Years in operation
 - c. Number of employees
2. What is the influence of intelligent high-speed development on human resource management of expressway operation enterprises?
3. How is the human resource management of expressway operation enterprise effective in terms of:
 - a. Hiring
 - b. Personnel management
 - c. Performance appraisal
 - d. Compensation and management
 - e. Training and development
4. What enhancement can be developed to enhance human resource management?

Methodology

Research Design

First of all, understand the relevant requirements of the paper and master the research methods and relevant theories applied in this paper so as to determine the direction and main line of paper writing and provide a good foundation for paper writing simply and quickly. Secondly, in the paper on the basis of the outline, the first to do is to the present situation of national policy and the popularity of high-speed wisdom, collected under the high speed universal wisdom, because of the popularity of intelligent high speed while driving the related questions of human resource management, combined with the real demand of enterprise, for S highway management company put forward the corresponding solutions, and refine technical routes and guidelines. Finally, I wrote the paper according to the technical route and guidelines, communicated with the teacher many times, corrected the imperfections of the paper in time, and wrote the paper in time according to the requirements of different nodes.

This paper studies the human resource management of high-speed operation enterprises in G province under the rapid development of intelligence by combining the literature research method, the case analysis method, and the questionnaire survey method. Literature research supplements the theoretical basis of previous studies and provides a supporting point, which can further enhance the theoretical value of this study. Meanwhile, the positive significance of this paper is that the theoretical research in this paper can improve and optimize the objectivity and systematicity of the research.

With the rapid development of intelligence, the data before and after the popularization of human resource management in a high-speed operation company S located in G province was collected through a questionnaire survey. Based on this, the current situation and problems of human resource management are analyzed. By case analysis, it is determined that S expressway operation company in G province will search for universal human resources in its business activities, optimize and guarantee the quality of the research process, promote and improve the human resource management of operators, and provide reasonable support for the rapid development of wisdom. The research in this paper is objective and accurate.

Data Collection Analysis

To ensure that the survey data are typical, representative, reasonable, and scientific, the author first consulted a large number of human resource management research studies and smart high-speed construction-related research literature through a literature review to formulate the overall research idea of the paper. Secondly, the author made use of the advantages of working in a high-speed operation company to solicit opinions, conduct interviews, and conduct a questionnaire survey after obtaining the consent of the management leaders and listening to their suggestions and countermeasures on the human resource management of the high-speed operation company under the construction of smart high-speed so as to lay the foundation for the following questionnaire research. Finally, based on Bai's work practice and his long-term working experience in operation management in S high-speed operation company, this paper conducts a systematic analysis and in-depth thinking on S high-speed operation company's human resource management, deliberates and revises the problems and structure of the questionnaire, and produces the final questionnaire for cost research.

To some extent, the construction of intelligent expressways reduces the burden of queuing vehicles in front of expressway stations, which is not only energy-saving and environmental protection but also convenient for drivers. In recent years, with the popularization of smart high-speed, there has been relatively much research on this aspect at home and abroad. The research mainly focuses on the comprehensive popularization of smart high-speed, which improves the efficiency of lane use, the accuracy of high-speed fee collection, and the collection and deduction of the updated cost of smart high-speed-related equipment and technology. Most of the research is aimed at improving equipment technology and optimizing related costs and regulations. However, there are few studies on the optimization of human resource management in expressway enterprises. Therefore, this research collects information about S company's personnel structure, age distribution, education level, recruitment situation, training situation, performance appraisal, and so on through a questionnaire survey so as to analyze the influence of the popularization of smart high-speed on S company and the human resource management situation. To provide theoretical support for the next step, put forward targeted suggestions.

Finally, combined with my own work practice in S high-speed operation enterprise and my long-term experience in charge of human resource management in S high-speed operation company, I conducted a systematic analysis and in-depth thinking on the human resource management of S company, examined and modified the questions and structure of the questionnaire, and produced the final questionnaire of the cost research. On the basis of the promise to keep personal information confidential, this questionnaire mainly analyzes the middle and senior managers of the company. Due to COVID-19 impact, the questionnaire was mainly sent by email. A total of 89 questionnaires were sent out in this survey, and 81 valid questionnaires were finally collected, with an effective recovery rate of 91%.

Results and Discussion

In recent years, with the popularity of ETC on expressways, there has been a lot of research in this field at home and abroad. The research mainly focuses on improving the use efficiency of special ETC lanes, the accuracy of collecting expressway tolls, the updating of ETC-related equipment and technology, and the updating of charging and deducting technology under the comprehensive popularization of electronic non-parking tolls. Most of the research is aimed at improving equipment technology and optimizing related costs and regulations. However, there are few studies on the human resource management optimization of highway enterprises.

Therefore, this paper takes the high-speed operation enterprise S as an example to investigate and collect the number of employees, toll amount, and traffic flow of Company A from 2018 to 2020. In 2018 and 2019, despite the impact of ETC project construction and the cancellation of provincial toll stations, as well as the novel coronavirus epidemic in 2020, from the beginning of February to the middle of May, all

vehicles on the expressway are exempt from the policy of highway toll, but the traffic flow and toll amount of the section under the company's control still show an increasing trend year by year. Due to the popularity of ETC, the total number of employees of the company changes relatively significantly. The survey statistics are as follows:

1. Gender structure. By the end of 2020, the male to female ratio of S high-speed operating company was 98:100, basically in line with the industry characteristics.

Figure 1. Gender structure

2. Age analysis. By the end of 2020, the average age of employees in S Highway company is between 35 and 40 years old. The age structure of employees in S company shows a normal distribution and tends to be younger than that in the same industry. The number of employees under 40 is 149, accounting for 68% of the total number of employees in Company S.

Figure 2. Age analysis

3. Seniority analysis. S Company was established in 2012. Due to the relatively stable nature of work in the company, employees are generally loyal to the company. By 2020, more than half of all employees have worked for more than five years.

Figure 3. Seniority analysis

4. Analysis of post structure. According to the nature of the company, the regular employees of S high-speed operation company can be roughly divided into five categories: middle-level management, general management, toll station management, first-line toll collection, and logistics support.

Figure 4. Analysis of post structure

5. Analysis of educational background. By the end of 2020, the survey found that the educational level of employees of S Highway Company is generally low, among which 33 employees have bachelor's degree or above, accounting for 14%, while only one employee has master's degree or above, accounting for less than 1% of the total number of employees in the company. There are 109 people with high school education or below, accounting for 49% of the total staff of S Company.

Figure 5. Analysis of educational background

6. Analysis of professional and technical personnel. By 2020, the survey found that there are eight people who have obtained professional technical qualifications in S Expressway Company, accounting for 3.6% of the total number of employees. Among them, one (1) senior title, two (2) junior titles, and five (5) intermediate titles.

Figure 6. Analysis of professional and technical personnel

Problems in Human Resource Management of a High-Speed Operation Company

1. Imperfect personnel diversion management. With the realization of the highway non-parking toll collection system, ETC users have become popular in our country. The comprehensive popularization of ETC will mean that the demand for toll collectors will be greatly reduced. In addition, because the work centers of high-speed operation companies are too concentrated, the work attributes of high-speed toll collection employees are relatively simple. In the same city, the staff demands of the parent company of the S high-speed operation company also gradually tend to be saturated, which will cause certain obstacles to the re-employment of high-speed toll collection employees. S high-speed operator is relatively large in scale but has a single business content. Most of them exist in the form of highway operation and maintenance. If employees want to engage in related industries according to their work experience and personal skills, there are fewer vacancies, and employees are under great pressure from competition. The operation of a high-speed operation company can almost monopolize a small area, and employees need to learn other skills to find a way out of re-employment. For some older workers, the competition and the status quo are no doubt cruel, increasing the work pressure on the company to downsize.

2. Ignoring job analysis and narrow recruitment channels. Regarding the recruitment of staff, the questionnaire contains four questions, mainly from the following aspects: whether the position has the job description formed by the analysis, whether the new staff is competent for the job, the completion of the job, whether the recruitment procedures are carried out in strict accordance with the norms, and what kinds of recruitment channels are available. The statistical analysis of the obtained data draws the following conclusions: first, it can be found that the overall evaluation of the company's employees is low in the whole process of recruitment. Secondly, the four indicators are investigated, respectively, and it is found that the assessment from high to low refers to the standardization of recruitment procedures, recruitment channels, job analysis, and finally the competency of the recruitment staff. More than half of mid- and senior-level leaders believe their hiring process is standardized, while less than 20% believe it has been extended. The rational analysis of the post is inextricably related to the function of professional ability, which is the condition and basis of the employee's post. Among them, the recognition rate of reasonable analysis of functions is higher (48.2%), followed by whether the personnel of the post is competent (46.9%).

3. Training content is boring, and the training method is traditional. Regarding training management, the questionnaire should include a review of the frequency of training, the extent to which training content meets employee needs, training interests, and training methods. In general, the respondents did not agree with the evaluation of the company's training management. The analysis shows that the degree of evaluation varies from top to bottom, and the interest in the training methods of S Company is more obvious in the field of training management. In terms of the number and proportion of enterprises established and the content of high-frequency training, employees must be interested in the content of training and learning. More than four indicators (the sum of highly approved and basic approved rates) should be used, which are 37.9%, 43.1%, 24.1%, and 15.2%, respectively. The disapproval rates were 27.9%, 21.6%, 57%, and 56.9%, respectively. These are the use of training methods that are dependent on training content but no longer interested in, and there are a lot of approved types that need to be solved in recruitment.

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. Measures to improve the effectiveness of personnel placement

First of all, it is necessary to improve relevant systems, properly solve the re-employment problem of employees, pay attention to reasonable methods in the implementation process, and actively and promptly deal with it. Many employees in the enterprise have worked for more than ten years, which means that each employee's job not only represents a job but also a part of his life.

Therefore, the redeployment caused by job changes also has a direct impact on employees' family lives. In the establishment of relevant systems, we must take into account various factors based on the basic situation of employees rather than a single system. Always emphasize the people-oriented concept.

On the other hand, although it is impossible to complete the task of relocating employees of high-speed operating companies in the short term, it is necessary to ensure that every employee is arranged to work to ensure mobilization and effectiveness. Some employees who are willing to be self-employed should be recognized and supported by the company and local authorities, but they cannot be forced to start their own businesses because these issues are more sensitive. It is easy to cause employee conflict.

Changing jobs and starting a business are ways for many companies to support their employees. Vigorously developing entrepreneurship is also an important way to readjust the direction of employees in a rapidly developing enterprise. First of all, there is a coordinated functional adjustment, which can promote the development of the enterprise through the introduction of internal policies for corporate transformation. Meanwhile, the enterprise will try its best to put forward valuable suggestions for future work based on the performance of employees and help employees adjust their career plans to meet the needs of the work and improve their personal abilities.

Under the comprehensive popularization of ETC in most high-speed companies, the work content of transferred employees is too simple, and once there is no purpose for job changes, they are likely to lack adaptability. Therefore, when determining the employees to be transferred, it is necessary to fully analyze and understand the situation of employees, determine the location of each employee, and ensure their presence. Secondly, employees who have the hope of starting their own businesses through their own efforts should be encouraged. For example, the transferred employees should provide some necessary support, such as setting up an entrepreneurship office to provide guidance and training specifically for the transferred employees to start their own businesses, so as to help them reduce the entrepreneurial problems caused by the single reason of early work in the entrepreneurial process. At the same time, highway operation enterprises can also apply to the local government to give some policy support and tax incentives to employees in the process of starting a business, so as to improve the enthusiasm of employees who transfer jobs to start a business in various aspects.

The enterprise should always know the ideas of employees for strengthening technical training. For some employees who want to start their own businesses and engage in technical work, the enterprise needs to strengthen the training of these employees and help them start their own businesses from various aspects, such as capital and technology. First of all, a high-speed operation company must pay more attention to its employees, be fully responsible for them, and have its own sense of social responsibility.

Under comprehensive popularization, the adjustment of employees' work in high-speed operation enterprises is inevitable and becomes an important problem faced by every enterprise. Secondly, because the working conditions of the personnel in high-speed operation companies are concentrated for a long time and because of the long hours of single work, the employees lack professional skills outside of work. Therefore, if an employee needs other skills, the enterprise should give full support and provide relevant training to improve the employee's adaptability and learning ability to a greater extent.

2. Development of scientific job descriptions and open up diversified recruitment channels

To solve the problem of ignoring job analysis and narrow recruitment channels, enterprises need to develop scientific job descriptions. Personnel working in the recruitment process should take the job descriptions of high-speed operating enterprises as the basis to obtain the professional and technical talents the company lacks through multiple channels.

Draft only in collaboration with staff from other offices. As mentioned above, the interviewees believe that there are some problems with the professional competence of the employees of the company, indicating that the talents needed by the company are inconsistent with the talents recruited or that they are not competent at work, which is bound to affect the operation of the company. Therefore, high-speed operation companies must analyze and formulate job descriptions from basic positions in combination with their own conditions, develop diversified talent introduction and recruitment channels, and rectify the system or related policies that have previously caused problems.

Job analysis is the most important work in human resource management. Proper examination of job requirements, the formation of a scientific job description, and long-term strictness in accordance with the rules and regulations to complete the work will be a significant contribution to the development of the enterprise and play a very important role in the optimization of human resources management.

3. Fairness and incentive of the compensation system

The establishment of a salary system should reflect the principle of fairness, including internal and external aspects of fairness. External equity requires the company to strengthen its position in the talent market, give rewards within the limited scope of financial opportunities, and allow leading rewards so that the company can recruit the right outstanding talents. Internal fairness is about making employees think that what they are paid is fair. Therefore, managers need to make timely suggestions on the salary system and establish an open, transparent, and fair salary system so as to effectively motivate employees to work. On the other hand, salaries must be able to motivate employees, which can be satisfactory. Employees vary in their working abilities, years of service, and skill levels, so their efforts for the company and the amount of work they put in are bound to vary. In order to effectively solve the problem of equal pay for equal work, the establishment of the compensation system should make the gap between employees' ability and contribution level to the enterprise be filled by those who make the greatest contribution to the improvement of employees' enthusiasm. Meanwhile, in order to reduce the difference, low-income employees should be encouraged to strive for greater employability and greater contribution.

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